

Comparative Review of Essential Oil Mechanisms and Clinical Evidence for Primary Dysmenorrhea Cramp Management

Revisión comparativa de aceites esenciales: mecanismos y evidencia clínica en dismenorrea primaria

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Abstract

[Objective] This study aimed to compare the pharmacological mechanisms, clinical evidence, and therapeutic potential of essential oils used for the management of primary dysmenorrhea and to identify the most promising candidates for evidence-based complementary therapy. **[Methodology]** A systematic literature review was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses 2020 guidelines. Literature published between 2021 and 2026 was retrieved from three international databases. After duplicate removal and eligibility assessment based on predefined inclusion criteria, 25 studies were included for qualitative synthesis. Data were extracted on study characteristics, essential oil type, active compounds, pharmacological mechanisms, administration methods, intervention duration, and clinical outcomes. The findings were synthesized through a comparative narrative analysis according to mechanism of action, effectiveness, safety profile, and strength of clinical evidence. **[Results]** The reviewed essential oils consistently demonstrated anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antispasmodic, and neuromodulatory activities that contributed to reducing menstrual pain and improving associated symptoms. Comparative analysis showed that ginger presented the strongest overall potential because of its multiple pharmacological targets, consistent clinical effectiveness, wide availability, and affordability. Peppermint exhibited rapid analgesic and antispasmodic effects, whereas lavender showed the most consistent clinical evidence together with relaxation and anxiolytic benefits. Other essential oils, including cinnamon, chamomile, bergamot, clary sage, and rose, also demonstrated promising therapeutic effects, although supporting evidence was comparatively limited. **[Conclusions]** Essential oils represent promising complementary interventions for primary dysmenorrhea. However, standardized clinical studies with larger populations are still required to strengthen the evidence and support broader clinical application.

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Keywords: primary dysmenorrhea; essential oils; aromatherapy; menstrual pain; complementary therapy; pharmacology; systematic literature review.

Resumen

[Objetivo] El objetivo de este estudio fue comparar los mecanismos farmacológicos, la evidencia clínica y el potencial terapéutico de los aceites esenciales utilizados para el tratamiento de la dismenorrea primaria, con el fin de identificar las alternativas más prometedoras como terapias complementarias basadas en evidencia. **[Metodología]** Se realizó una revisión sistemática de la literatura siguiendo las directrices de Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses 2020. Se buscaron publicaciones entre 2021 y 2026 en tres bases de datos internacionales. Tras eliminar los registros duplicados y aplicar los criterios de inclusión previamente establecidos, se seleccionaron 25 estudios para el análisis cualitativo. Se extrajeron datos sobre las características de los estudios, el tipo de aceite esencial, los compuestos activos, los mecanismos farmacológicos, las vías de administración, la duración de la intervención y los resultados clínicos. Los hallazgos se sintetizaron mediante un análisis narrativo comparativo. **[Resultados]** Los aceites esenciales mostraron actividades antiinflamatorias, analgésicas, antiespasmódicas y neuromoduladoras asociadas con la reducción del dolor menstrual y la mejoría de los síntomas relacionados. El jengibre presentó el mayor potencial terapéutico debido a sus múltiples mecanismos farmacológicos, evidencia clínica consistente, amplia disponibilidad y bajo costo. La menta mostró un efecto analgésico y antiespasmódico rápido, mientras que la lavanda presentó la evidencia clínica más consistente junto con beneficios relajantes y ansiolíticos. Otros aceites esenciales también demostraron efectos prometedores, aunque con evidencia clínica más limitada. **[Conclusiones]** Los aceites esenciales constituyen una alternativa complementaria prometedora para el manejo de la dismenorrea primaria; sin embargo, se requieren estudios clínicos estandarizados con muestras más amplias para fortalecer la evidencia disponible.

Keywords: dismenorrea primaria; aceites esenciales; aromaterapia; dolor menstrual; terapia complementaria; farmacología; revisión sistemática.

Introduction

Primary dysmenorrhea is one of the most common gynecological disorders among women of reproductive age, affecting approximately 50–90 % of women worldwide (Fatwa et al., 2025; Bharati et al., 2026). It is characterized by painful cramping in the lower abdomen occurring shortly before or during menstruation in the absence of identifiable pelvic pathology (Bharati et al., 2026). The pain may radiate to the lower back and thighs and is often accompanied by systemic symptoms such as nausea, diarrhea, headache, and fatigue, significantly affecting women's daily activities, academic performance, work productivity, and overall quality of life (Ma et al., 2026).

prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂), which induce uterine hypercontractility, vasoconstriction, and ischemia, ultimately leading to menstrual pain (Bharati et al., 2026; Xu et al., 2020).

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and hormonal contraceptives remain the first-line treatments for primary dysmenorrhea. NSAIDs reduce prostaglandin synthesis through cyclooxygenase inhibition, whereas hormonal contraceptives suppress ovulation and endometrial proliferation, thereby decreasing prostaglandin production during menstruation (Ma et al., 2026). However, the long-term use of these therapies may be limited by adverse effects. NSAIDs have been associated with

The pathophysiology of primary dysmenorrhea has been closely linked to excessive production of prostaglandins, particularly prostaglandin F_{2α} (PGF_{2α}) and changes, irregular bleeding, and an increased risk of thromboembolic events in susceptible individuals (Ma et al., 2026). These limitations have encouraged the exploration of safer and more acceptable complementary approaches for managing menstrual pain.

Among the various complementary therapies available, aromatherapy using essential oils has gained increasing attention because of its potential therapeutic benefits and relatively favorable safety profile. Essential oils are volatile compounds derived from different parts of plants, including flowers, leaves, stems, roots, bark, and fruits. Recent studies have reported their potential use in alleviating symptoms associated with primary dysmenorrhea and improving women's well-being (Bharati et al., 2026; Zhao et al., 2022).

In recent years, a growing body of evidence has investigated the effectiveness of different essential oils in the management of primary dysmenorrhea. Lavender essential oil has been among the most extensively studied, with reports indicating its potential to reduce menstrual pain and promote relaxation. Peppermint has also demonstrated beneficial effects, although some studies have been limited by short intervention durations (Lagzian et al., 2025). In addition, bergamot, grapefruit, clary sage, chamomile, and combinations of essential oils have shown promising clinical outcomes in reducing menstrual pain and related symptoms (Özer et al., 2025; Kobayashi et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022; Shabani et al., 2022). Despite these encouraging findings, the

gastrointestinal disturbances and mild neurological symptoms, while hormonal contraceptives may cause nausea, breast tenderness, mood

administration methods, intervention durations, and outcome measurements. Furthermore, most studies have focused on individual essential oils, resulting in limited information regarding comparative effectiveness, differences in mechanisms of action, and the overall strength of clinical evidence among various essential oils used for primary dysmenorrhea. Consequently, a comprehensive synthesis identifying the most promising essential oils for complementary management of primary dysmenorrhea is still lacking.

Therefore, this review aims to provide a comparative analysis of the clinical evidence regarding various essential oils used in the management of menstrual pain associated with primary dysmenorrhea. The findings of this review are expected to contribute to evidence-based recommendations and support the development of safer and more standardized complementary approaches to improve women's quality of life.

Theoretical Framework

Primary dysmenorrhea is defined as painful, spasmodic uterine contractions in the lower abdomen occurring in the absence of identifiable pelvic pathology, primarily driven by the overproduction and release of endometrial prostaglandins such as PGF_{2α} and PGE₂ during menstruation (Bharati et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022). This biological process is initiated by a decline in progesterone levels during the late luteal phase, which activates the arachidonic acid cascade and elevates the activity of cyclooxygenase (COX)

available evidence remains scattered and heterogeneous.

A major limitation of the current literature is the substantial variability in study designs, dosage regimens, arteries, resulting in transient uterine ischemia and the stimulation of pain-sensitive nerve endings (Bharati et al., 2026; Ristiani et al., 2021). Furthermore, recent clinical evidence suggests that an oxidative microenvironment exacerbates tissue damage and lowers the threshold for pain perception, highlighting the role of oxidative stress in the intensity of cramps (Kobayashi et al., 2026; Sahebi & Kakhki, 2026). Essential oils manage these multifaceted symptoms by acting as natural anti-inflammatory agents that inhibit the COX-2 enzyme pathway and reduce the biosynthesis of inflammatory mediators (Sahebi & Kakhki, 2026; Saud et al., 2022).

The pharmacological efficacy of essential oils is further enhanced by bioactive constituents such as linalool and cinnamaldehyde, which exert direct antispasmodic effects by blocking voltage-gated calcium channels and promoting uterine smooth muscle relaxation (Bharati et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022). Psychophysiological relief is mediated through the olfactory system, where inhaled volatile molecules stimulate the limbic system to trigger the neurochemical release of neurotransmitters like endorphins and serotonin, which serve as natural analgesics and mood modulators (Bharati et al., 2026; Najaf Najafi et al., 2021). For topical applications involving massage, the gate control theory of pain provides a relevant theoretical basis, suggesting that cutaneous stimulation sends rapid signals via large-diameter nerve fibers to "close the gate" on slower pain impulses at the spinal cord (Najaf

enzymes (Bharati et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022). These prostanoids induce myometrial hypercontractility and potent vasoconstriction of the uterine spiral (Kobayashi et al., 2026; Zyburtowicz et al., 2024). Together, these synergistic pharmacological and sensory mechanisms offer a comprehensive framework for the use of essential oils as a non-invasive complementary approach to primary dysmenorrhea management (Lagzian et al., 2025; Ristiani et al., 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a **Systematic Literature Review (SLR)** using a qualitative approach to systematically identify, critically evaluate, and synthesize scientific evidence regarding the use of essential oils for the management of primary dysmenorrhea. A systematic review was selected because it provides a structured, transparent, and reproducible method for integrating findings from multiple scientific studies. The review aimed to summarize current evidence on the anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antispasmodic effects of essential oils while comparing their pharmacological mechanisms and clinical effectiveness in relieving menstrual pain. The review process followed the **Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020** guidelines, including article identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and final study inclusion. The population of this review consisted of published scientific articles investigating essential oils for primary dysmenorrhea, with **35** eligible studies included in the final qualitative synthesis.

Najafi et al., 2021). Additionally, the potent antioxidant properties of essential oils help neutralize free radicals and mitigate the oxidative stress associated with chronic menstrual cramping databases: **PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, and ScienceDirect**. These databases were selected because of their extensive coverage of biomedical, pharmacological, and clinical research. Only articles published between **2021 and 2026** were included to ensure that the review reflected the most recent scientific evidence. Articles published in English and Indonesian were considered eligible, although English-language publications were prioritized because they represent the majority of internationally indexed literature.

The search strategy was developed using the **PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome)** framework. The primary keywords included the following terms:

Table 1

Keywords based on PICO components

PICO Components	Primary Keywords
Population	Primary dysmenorrhea, menstrual pain, dysmenorrhea, primary dysmenorrhea, menstrual pain
Intervention	Essential oil, aromatherapy, peppermint oil, ginger oil, cinnamon oil, essential oil, aromatherapy
Comparison	Placebo, conventional therapy, NSAID, analgesic, conventional therapy
Outcome	Pain relief, pain intensity, VAS, NRS, prostaglandin, anti-inflammatory, analgesic effect

Note: Derived from the present study.

Additional synonyms and related terms, including botanical names and alternative clinical terminology, were incorporated to maximize search sensitivity and minimize the possibility of missing relevant studies. Database-specific filters were subsequently applied according to publication year, language, and article type. Reference lists of eligible studies were also manually examined to identify

Literature Search

A comprehensive literature search was conducted between **March and April 2026** using three international electronic study characteristics were recorded using a standardized Microsoft Excel data extraction form.

Study Selection

Literature selection followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines to ensure that only relevant, high-quality studies meeting the predefined inclusion criteria were included. The selection process was conducted independently by two researchers, with disagreements resolved through discussion until consensus was reached. The complete study selection process is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Distribution of articles retrieved from each database.

No.	Database	Number of Articles	Percentage
1	PubMed / MEDLINE	19 articles	24,7%
2	ScienceDirect (Elsevier)	21 articles	27,3%
3	Scopus	37 articles	48,1%
Total articles		77 articles	100%

Note: Derived from the present study.

The database search identified **77 records**, consisting of **19 articles from PubMed/MEDLINE, 21 from ScienceDirect, and 37 from Scopus** (Table 1). After removing **12 duplicate records, 65 unique articles** remained for title and abstract screening. Studies that did not investigate essential oils for primary dysmenorrhea or failed to address the research objectives were excluded during methodological quality and were retained to strengthen the reliability of the evidence synthesis.

additional relevant publications. All retrieved records were managed using reference management software, while this stage. The remaining studies subsequently underwent full-text assessment based on predefined eligibility criteria, including study population, intervention, outcomes, and methodological quality. Following the eligibility assessment, **25 studies** fulfilled all inclusion criteria and were included in the final qualitative synthesis.

Table 3
Summary of the Number of Articles at Each Stage of Literature Selection

No.	Selection stage	Records remaining	Records excluded
1	Identification through databases (PubMed + ScienceDirect + Scopus)	77	—
2	Removal of duplicates	65	12
3	Title and abstract screening	37	28
4	Evaluation of topic suitability and PICO	37	0
5	Selection of full-text articles	25	12
	Final articles included	25	—

Study quality assessment

The methodological quality of all included studies was assessed using the **Jadad Scale** for randomized controlled trials. This instrument evaluates three methodological domains, namely randomization, blinding, and reporting of participant withdrawals or dropouts. Jadad scores range from **0 to 5**, with higher scores indicating better methodological quality and lower risk of bias. Studies scoring **three or higher** were considered to have adequate
The selection process is presented in the PRISMA 2020 Diagram.

Data extraction

Relevant information from each eligible study was extracted using a standardized data extraction form. The extracted variables included the first author, publication year, country of origin, study design, participant characteristics, sample size, type of essential oil, major bioactive compounds, application method, dosage, intervention duration, outcome measures, and principal findings. The primary outcome was the reduction in menstrual pain intensity, whereas secondary outcomes included pain duration, anxiety, quality of life, additional analgesic use, and reported adverse events.

Data synthesis

Because substantial heterogeneity existed among the included studies regarding study design, essential oil type, intervention protocol, dosage, treatment duration, and outcome measures, a quantitative meta-analysis was not performed. Instead, a **qualitative narrative synthesis** was conducted. Studies were grouped according to the type of essential oil, pharmacological mechanism, application method, and reported clinical outcomes. Comparative analyses were subsequently performed to evaluate differences in effectiveness, mechanisms of action, safety profiles, and consistency of findings across studies. The final synthesis integrated all available evidence to provide a comprehensive comparison of the pharmacological mechanisms and clinical effectiveness of essential oils for the management of primary dysmenorrhea.

This review synthesized evidence from randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses investigating the effectiveness of essential oils for primary dysmenorrhea. Overall, essential oils administered through inhalation, massage, or oral supplementation reduced menstrual pain, although their effectiveness varied depending on the type of essential oil, dosage, and route of administration.

Primary Dysmenorrhea and the Mechanism of Menstrual Pain

Primary dysmenorrhea is menstrual pain without identifiable pelvic pathology, characterized by cramping lower abdominal pain before or during menstruation and often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, headache, and fatigue (Bharati et al., 2026; Ma et al., 2026). As one of the most common gynecological disorders among women of reproductive age, it can impair daily activities and quality of life.

The condition mainly results from hormonal changes during the menstrual cycle. At the end of the luteal phase, declining progesterone triggers endometrial shedding and activates phospholipase A₂, releasing arachidonic acid from cell membranes (Bharati et al., 2026). Through the cyclooxygenase (COX) pathway, arachidonic acid is converted into prostaglandins, particularly prostaglandin F_{2α} (PGF_{2α}) and prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂), the key mediators of primary dysmenorrhea (Bharati et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022). Therefore, prostaglandin overproduction is considered the main cause of menstrual pain and the primary target of treatment.

Figure 1. Pathogenesis and Clinical Manifestations of Primary Dysmenorrhea. A decline in progesterone levels and increased prostaglandin production trigger excessive uterine contractions, inflammation, and various clinical manifestations associated with primary dysmenorrhea.

Source: Adapted from Ma et al. (2026).

Role of Prostaglandins, Uterine Contractions, and Inflammation in Primary Dysmenorrhea

Women with primary dysmenorrhea generally have higher $\text{PGF}2\alpha$ and $\text{PGE}2$ levels than those without menstrual pain (Bharati et al., 2026; Saud et al., 2022).

prostaglandins are central to uterine contraction, ischemia, and inflammation, inhibiting their synthesis remains the main therapeutic approach. This underlies the effectiveness of NSAIDs, while their limited efficacy and potential adverse effects have prompted interest in alternative therapies, including essential oils with anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antispasmodic properties.

Characteristics and Bioactive Compounds of Essential Oils

This section summarizes the botanical characteristics, major bioactive compounds, and pharmacological activities of the essential oils included in this review, providing a basis for understanding their therapeutic effects against primary dysmenorrhea.

1. Peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.)

Peppermint essential oil, obtained by steam distillation of fresh leaves and stems, contains over 100 volatile compounds, mainly menthol (35–55%) and menthone (14–32%) (Zhao et al., 2022; Armatys et al., 2025). Menthol exerts analgesic and antispasmodic effects by activating TRPM8 receptors and reducing calcium influx into smooth muscle cells, thereby decreasing uterine contractions. Menthone enhances these effects through anti-inflammatory activity by suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines such as $\text{IL-1}\beta$ and $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ (Zhao et al., 2022; Baser et al., 2025; Lagzian et al., 2025).

2. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe)

Ginger essential oil is rich in [6]-gingerol and [6]-shogaol, which are responsible for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities. Gingerol inhibits COX-2, 5-LOX, and NF- κ B signaling, reducing prostaglandin synthesis and inflammation, while shogaol modulates TRPV1 receptors to decrease pain

PGF2 α enhances uterine contractions and vasoconstriction, reducing uterine blood flow and causing ischemia and tissue hypoxia that activate nociceptors and produce cramping pain (Bharati et al., 2026; Ristiani et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2026).

Prostaglandins also stimulate local inflammation and the release of pro-inflammatory mediators, contributing to symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, dizziness, and fatigue (Ma et al., 2026; Masoumi et al., 2016). Since hypersensitivity (Negi et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020; Meilani et al., 2025).

3. Cinnamon (*Cinnamomum* spp.)

The major bioactive compounds in cinnamon essential oil are trans-cinnamaldehyde and eugenol. Cinnamaldehyde suppresses COX-2 expression, prostaglandin production, and inflammatory cytokines, whereas eugenol provides analgesic effects through COX-2 inhibition and blockade of voltage-gated sodium channels (Xu et al., 2020; Saud et al., 2022; Zaen, 2021).

4. Rose (*Rosa damascena* Mill.)

Rose essential oil mainly contains citronellol, geraniol, and phenethyl alcohol. Citronellol reduces prostaglandin synthesis and promotes smooth muscle relaxation, geraniol inhibits NF- κ B signaling to exert anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects, and phenethyl alcohol contributes mild antispasmodic and anxiolytic activities (Koohpayeh et al., 2021; Shabani et al., 2022).

5. Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia* Mill.)

Lavender essential oil is characterized by linalool (25–45%) and linalyl acetate (25–47%) (Song & Oh, 2025). Linalool produces sedative and analgesic effects through GABAergic modulation, while linalyl acetate

contributes anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic activities. Clinical studies have shown that inhalation and massage aromatherapy with lavender significantly reduce pain intensity in primary dysmenorrhea (Kumalasari et al., 2022; Fatwa et al., 2025).

6. Bergamot (*Citrus bergamia* Risso) and Grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi* Macfad.)

Bergamot and grapefruit essential oils have recently shown clinical potential in managing menstrual pain. Inhalation of both oils during the luteal phase

significantly reduced premenstrual and menstrual pain. Bergamot, rich in linalool and linalyl acetate, exerts anxiolytic and analgesic effects through GABAergic and serotonergic modulation, whereas grapefruit, dominated by limonene (up to 90%), reduces inflammatory mediator production and modulates the HPA axis to lessen cortisol-related pain amplification. Both oils also act through olfactory-limbic pathways, promoting parasympathetic activity, endorphin release, and reduced pain perception (Özer et al., 2025; Sattayakhom et al., 2023; Liang et al., 2023).

Comparison of Bioactive Compounds and Pharmacological Activities

The following table summarizes the major bioactive compounds and pharmacological activities of the essential oils included in this review.

Table 4

Major bioactive compounds and pharmacological activities of essential oils in the management of primary dysmenorrhea

Essential Oil	Major Bioactive Compounds	Mechanism of Action	Anti-inflammatory	Analgesic/Antispasmodic	Evidence
Peppermint (<i>Mentha piperita</i>)	Menthol (35–55%) Menthone (14–32%)	Agonist TRPM8; blocks Ca^{2+} ; inhibits COX-2	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	++
Ginger (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	Gingerol (major) Shogaol	Inhibits COX-2 & 5-LOX; blocks NF- κ B; agonist TRPV1	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	+++
Cinnamon (<i>Cinnamomum</i> spp.)	Cinnamaldehyde (55–90%) Eugenol	Inhibits COX-2; peroxyl radical scavenger; blocks PGE ₂ , IL-6, TNF- α ; blocks VGSC	✓✓✓	✓✓	++
Rose damascena (<i>Rosa damascena</i>)	Citronellol (18–55%) Geraniol (10–22%) Phenethyl alcohol	Inhibits COX-2; modulates cAMP; blocks NF- κ B	✓✓	✓✓	++
Lavender (<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>)	Linalool (25–45%) Linalyl acetate (25–47%)	Modulates GABA-A; schiff; antispasmodic; antiinflamm	✓✓	✓✓	+++
Bergamot bergamia (<i>Citrus bergamia</i>)	Linalool (11–22%) Linalyl acetate (17–40%) Limonene (27–52%)	GABAergic & serotonergic modulation; limbic activation; sympathetic suppression	✓✓	✓✓	Emerging
Grapefruit paradisi (<i>Citrus paradisi</i>)	Limonene (up to 90%) Myrcene Nootkatone	Inflammatory mediator inhibition; HPA axis modulation; limbic-olfactory pathway activation	✓✓	✓✓	Emerging

Note: ✓✓✓ = strong; ✓✓ = moderate; ✓ = weak; +++ = extensive clinical evidence; ++ = moderate evidence; + = limited evidence.

Note: Derived from the present study.

Mechanisms of Essential Oils in the Management of Primary Dysmenorrhea

Essential oils may alleviate the multifactorial symptoms of primary dysmenorrhea through complementary mechanisms, including anti-inflammatory effects that suppress prostaglandin production, antispasmodic actions that relax uterine smooth muscle, neuromodulatory effects via the olfactory-limbic pathway, antioxidant activity, and sensory modulation associated with massage application (Bharati et al., 2026; Najaf Najafi et al., 2021). These mechanisms act synergistically to reduce pain and improve well-being.

1. Anti-inflammatory mechanisms

Anti-inflammatory activity is one of the main mechanisms underlying the use of essential oils in primary dysmenorrhea. Because

excessive prostaglandin production contributes to uterine hypercontractility, vasoconstriction, tissue hypoxia, and pain sensitization, suppressing inflammatory mediators is a key therapeutic target.

Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) reduces inflammation mainly through menthol-mediated inhibition of the ERK–NF- κ B pathway, lowering TNF- α and IL-1 β production. Its antioxidant constituents, such as rosmarinic acid and flavonoids, also reduce oxidative stress (Zhao et al., 2022; Baser et al., 2025). Ginger inhibits both cyclooxygenase (COX) and 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX) through gingerol and shogaol, decreasing prostaglandin and leukotriene synthesis. Meanwhile, cinnamon (*Cinnamomum cassia*) suppresses COX activity and COX-2 expression through cinnamaldehyde and eugenol, reducing prostaglandin E₂ production (Saud et al., 2022). Overall, ginger exhibits the broadest anti-inflammatory action by targeting multiple arachidonic acid pathways, whereas peppermint and cinnamon act through more specific targets.

2. Antispasmodic mechanisms

Excessive uterine contractions are a major cause of pain in primary dysmenorrhea. Elevated PGF_{2 α} increases myometrial contractions and uterine vasoconstriction, leading to increased intrauterine pressure, reduced blood flow, tissue hypoxia, and pain. Since myometrial contraction largely depends on intracellular Ca²⁺ influx, calcium signaling is an important therapeutic target.

Peppermint and cinnamon show the most direct antispasmodic effects. Menthol blocks voltage-gated calcium channels, reducing intracellular Ca²⁺ influx and promoting myometrial relaxation (Zhao et al., 2022). Similarly, cinnamon exerts

tocolytic effects by inhibiting extracellular calcium entry into uterine smooth muscle cells (Saud et al., 2022). Ginger acts more indirectly by reducing uterine sensitivity to prostaglandins and oxytocin, thereby decreasing contraction frequency and intensity (Xu et al., 2020). Thus, peppermint and cinnamon directly relieve uterine hypercontractility, whereas ginger primarily modulates upstream mediators.

3. Analgesic Mechanisms

The analgesic effects of essential oils involve both central nervous system modulation and direct interactions with sensory receptors. Inhaled volatile compounds stimulate olfactory pathways that project to the limbic system and hypothalamus, promoting relaxation, reducing sympathetic activity, and modulating pain perception. Lavender and bergamot have been clinically associated with reduced dysmenorrheic pain (Sattayakhom et al., 2023).

At the molecular level, essential oils modulate transient receptor potential (TRP) channels involved in nociception, including TRPV1, TRPM8, and TRPA1. Menthol activates TRPM8 to produce cooling sensations and analgesia, while menthol and eugenol can inhibit TRPV1, reducing pain transmission (Moroz et al., 2026; Li et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Schematic Representation of the Analgesic Mechanisms of Essential Oil Components (e.g., Menthol) in the Nervous System.

Source: Adapted from Li et al. (2022).

Menthol modulates TRPM8 and TRPA1 channels in dorsal root and trigeminal ganglia in a concentration-dependent manner. Low to moderate concentrations activate TRPM8 to induce cooling sensations, whereas higher concentrations may trigger cold allodynia. Central analgesia is further mediated through group II/III metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluRs) and endogenous κ -opioid pathways (Li et al., 2022).

Essential oils also enhance parasympathetic activity, lowering heart rate and systolic blood pressure. Together with inhibition of L-type calcium channels, these effects promote systemic relaxation and may attenuate excessive uterine contractions (Sattayakhom et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022).

4. Relaxation and Psychophysiological Effects

The relaxation effects of aromatherapy are closely linked to olfactory and central nervous system pathways. Volatile compounds stimulate olfactory receptors and activate limbic structures involved in emotion and memory, subsequently influencing the hypothalamus to promote endorphin release. These endogenous analgesics contribute to pain relief, relaxation, and improved psychological well-being during menstruation (Ristiani et al., 2021).

Figure 3. Mechanisms by Which Essential Oils (EOs) Reach the Brain Through the Olfactory, Respiratory, and Dermal Pathways.

Source: Adapted from Liang et al. (2023).

The figure illustrates how essential oil constituents affect the brain through olfactory pathways, pulmonary absorption, and dermal uptake, ultimately modulating autonomic function and pain perception (Liang et al., 2023).

Stress and anxiety can exacerbate menstrual pain by increasing neuroendocrine responses associated with uterine contractions (Ristiani et al., 2021). Essential oils rich in linalool and linalyl acetate, such as lavender, as well as *Citrus aurantium*, have demonstrated anxiolytic effects that promote relaxation and emotional well-being (Tan et al., 2023). By reducing psychological distress, aromatherapy may improve pain tolerance and lessen the perceived intensity of dysmenorrheic cramps (Liang et al., 2023).

Figure 4. Ranking Probability Plot Showing the Relative Effectiveness of Different Essential Oils in Reducing State Anxiety Inventory (SAIS) and Trait Anxiety Inventory (TAIS) Scores.

Source: Adapted from Tan et al. (2023).

The figure shows that *Jasminum sambac* had the highest probability of reducing state anxiety, whereas *Citrus aurantium* ranked highest for trait anxiety, with lemon and lavender also demonstrating favorable effects. These findings may guide the

selection of essential oils to address psychological factors influencing pain perception (Tan et al., 2023).

Clinical studies consistently report that aromatherapy delivered through inhalation or massage significantly reduces anxiety in individuals experiencing pain (Hedigan et al., 2023). Decreased salivary cortisol levels further support its stress-relieving effects. By alleviating stress and anxiety, aromatherapy may improve coping ability and reduce the perceived severity of primary dysmenorrhea as part of a holistic non-pharmacological approach (Tan et al., 2023).

Comparative Clinical Evidence of Essential Oils

Clinical evidence from systematic reviews indicates that essential oils and other complementary therapies effectively reduce pain intensity in primary dysmenorrhea (Ma et al., 2026; Ristiani et al., 2021). Aromatherapy acts by stimulating the limbic system through olfactory pathways, activating the hypothalamus to promote endorphin release as natural analgesics (Ristiani et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2026). In addition, bioactive compounds such as menthol in peppermint exhibit antispasmodic effects by inhibiting calcium channels, promoting uterine smooth muscle relaxation and pain relief (Lagzian et al., 2025).

Clinical evidence also suggests that the effectiveness of essential oils varies depending on the route of administration, including inhalation, topical massage, and oral use (Lagzian et al., 2025; Ristiani et al., 2021). Greater pain reduction has been reported when aromatherapy is combined with non-pharmacological interventions such as effleurage massage,

As reflected by improvements in Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) scores (Ma et al., 2026; Ristiani et al., 2021). Furthermore, essential oils generally have favorable safety profiles and fewer gastrointestinal adverse effects than conventional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) (Lagzian et al., 2025; Ma et al., 2026).

Clinical Effectiveness of Peppermint

Clinical evidence suggests that peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) effectively reduces pain intensity in women with primary dysmenorrhea. Systematic reviews of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have shown that oral peppermint preparations significantly lower pain scores compared with placebo and demonstrate efficacy comparable to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as mefenamic acid. Peppermint may also relieve gastrointestinal symptoms, including nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea, making it a suitable option for women with gastric sensitivity (Kusnianto et al., 2023; Lagzian et al., 2025).

Peppermint has also shown benefits when administered through inhalation, significantly reducing menstrual pain and promoting relaxation (Fatwa et al., 2025). These effects are mainly attributed to menthol, which exerts antispasmodic and analgesic actions through calcium channel inhibition and TRPM8 activation, resulting in uterine smooth muscle relaxation and reduced pain perception (Zhao et al., 2022). Overall, peppermint appears to be a safe and accessible complementary therapy for improving the quality of life of women with primary dysmenorrhea (Lagzian et al., 2025).

Clinical Effectiveness of Ginger

Clinical evidence consistently supports the effectiveness of ginger in reducing the severity of primary dysmenorrhea. Meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have shown that oral ginger supplementation significantly decreases menstrual pain compared with placebo and provides pain relief comparable to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as ibuprofen and mefenamic acid, making it a promising alternative for women seeking to avoid NSAID-related gastrointestinal adverse effects (Negi et al., 2021).

These effects are mainly attributed to gingerol and shogaol, which inhibit prostaglandin synthesis and exert anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic activities that relax uterine smooth muscle and relieve menstrual cramps. Clinical studies in adolescents have also demonstrated significant reductions in pain severity following ginger intervention. Together with its favorable safety profile and minimal adverse effects, ginger represents a safe and effective complementary therapy for primary dysmenorrhea (Meilani et al., 2025; Negi et al., 2021).

Clinical Effectiveness of Cinnamon

Clinical evidence suggests that cinnamon (*Cinnamomum verum* or *Cinnamomum burmanii*) effectively reduces pain intensity in primary dysmenorrhea. Studies in adolescents have consistently reported improvements in menstrual pain, while clinical trials have shown that oral cinnamon, particularly when combined with honey, significantly reduces pain scores from moderate to mild intensity. Inhalation aromatherapy with cinnamon essential oil has also been found to relieve pain and promote

relaxation through rapid olfactory–limbic stimulation (Sitorus et al., 2026; Zaen, 2021).

These effects are mainly attributed to cinnamaldehyde and eugenol. Cinnamaldehyde promotes uterine smooth muscle relaxation through its antispasmodic activity, whereas eugenol inhibits prostaglandin biosynthesis, reducing excessive uterine contractions. Combined with its favorable safety profile and accessibility, cinnamon represents a promising complementary therapy for primary dysmenorrhea (Sitorus et al., 2026; Zaen, 2021).

Clinical Effectiveness of Rose

Clinical evidence supports the effectiveness of rose aromatherapy, particularly *Rosa damascena*, in alleviating primary dysmenorrhea. Rose essential oil exhibits analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antispasmodic properties that may reduce menstrual pain by modulating prostaglandin levels. Studies have shown that abdominal massage or inhalation with rose oil significantly decreases pain intensity and may shorten pain duration, especially when diluted with carrier oils such as almond oil (Shabani et al., 2022; Yıldız et al., 2023).

These effects are partly mediated through olfactory stimulation of the central nervous system, promoting the release of endorphins and enkephalins while enhancing parasympathetic activity (Koochpayeh et al., 2021). Meta-analytic evidence also suggests that rose aromatherapy may relieve accompanying symptoms such as headache, fatigue, and bloating. Together with its favorable safety profile and minimal adverse effects, rose essential oil represents a promising

holistic complementary therapy for women with primary dysmenorrhea (Koochpayeh et al., 2021).

Clinical Effectiveness of Lavender

Clinical evidence consistently supports the effectiveness of lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) in reducing pain associated with primary dysmenorrhea. A meta-analysis of seven randomized controlled trials (RCTs) showed that lavender significantly decreased pain scores compared with placebo, making it one of the most effective non-pharmacological interventions for menstrual pain. Inhalation appears more effective than massage, likely due to rapid activation of olfactory pathways linked to the limbic system and cerebral cortex (Song & Oh, 2025).

These effects are mainly attributed to linalool and linalyl acetate, which possess sedative, mild anesthetic, and uterine muscle-relaxing properties. Lavender inhalation has also been associated with increased endorphin and serotonin release, promoting relaxation and enhancing pain tolerance. In addition, lavender may enhance transdermal drug delivery while providing anti-inflammatory and antioxidant benefits. Given its safety, accessibility, and minimal adverse effects, lavender represents a valuable complementary therapy for reducing menstrual discomfort and dependence on oral analgesics in women with primary dysmenorrhea (Kumalasari et al., 2022; Zyburtowicz et al., 2024).

Clinical Effectiveness of Clary Sage

Clinical evidence suggests that clary sage (*Salvia sclarea*) is an effective complementary therapy for primary dysmenorrhea. Randomized crossover trials have shown that inhalation of clary sage significantly reduces menstrual pain

and improves psychological symptoms such as anxiety, irritability, and sleep disturbances, thereby enhancing overall well-being during menstruation (Kobayashi et al., 2026). Rich in linalyl acetate, linalool, and sclareol, clary sage has long been used to relieve menstrual discomfort and support women's reproductive health (Jan et al., 2026).

These effects are attributed to its ability to inhibit PGF₂α-induced uterine contractions through modulation of calcium signaling pathways, reducing uterine hypercontractility and ischemia. Inhalation has also been associated with increased salivary antioxidant capacity, while linalyl acetate and linalool provide anxiolytic and sedative effects through autonomic nervous system regulation (Kobayashi et al., 2026; Son et al., 2025). Combined with its favorable safety profile and minimal risk of irritation or hormonal disruption, clary sage represents a practical and minimally invasive complementary approach for managing primary dysmenorrhea (Jan et al., 2026).

Clinical Effectiveness of Chamomile

Clinical evidence supports the effectiveness of chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) in managing primary dysmenorrhea through its anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic properties. By inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase pathways, chamomile reduces prostaglandin and leukotriene synthesis involved in uterine hypercontractility and menstrual pain. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have shown that chamomile provides pain relief comparable to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as mefenamic acid, while also reducing

menstrual bleeding volume (Niazi & Moradi, 2021; Shabani et al., 2022).

These effects are attributed to bioactive compounds including apigenin, α-bisabolol, and chamazulene, which possess anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, and mild sedative activities. In addition to relieving menstrual cramps, chamomile may improve symptoms such as headache, dizziness, fatigue, back pain, and mood disturbances. Together with its favorable safety profile and minimal adverse effects, chamomile represents a well-tolerated complementary therapy for women with primary dysmenorrhea (Dai et al., 2023; Shabani et al., 2022).

Clinical Effectiveness of Fennel

Clinical evidence consistently supports the effectiveness of fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) in managing primary dysmenorrhea. Randomized clinical trials and meta-analyses have shown that fennel significantly reduces pain intensity, cramp duration, and symptoms such as nausea and fatigue. Its analgesic efficacy is comparable to conventional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), including ibuprofen and mefenamic acid, while placebo-controlled trials have demonstrated sustained reductions in Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores across menstrual cycles (Rezvani Kakhki & Sahebi, 2026; Najafabadi et al., 2023). These effects are mainly attributed to trans-anethole, which suppresses prostaglandin synthesis through COX-2 inhibition and modulates voltage-gated calcium channels, reducing uterine hypercontractility and ischemia. Together with its spasmolytic and analgesic properties, fennel has a favorable safety profile with only mild and infrequent adverse effects, supporting its use as a safe

and promising complementary therapy, particularly for women who are intolerant to NSAIDs or prefer non-hormonal approaches to primary dysmenorrhea management (Rezvani Kakhki & Sahebi, 2026; Ma et al., 2026).

Clinical Effectiveness of Bergamot

Clinical evidence suggests that bergamot essential oil (*Citrus bergamia*) significantly improves psychological and physiological symptoms during the premenstrual phase. A randomized controlled trial involving 90 women showed that inhalation of pure bergamot oil for 30 minutes, three times daily over three menstrual cycles, significantly reduced total premenstrual syndrome (PMS) scores, including depressive affect, irritability, appetite changes, and pain perception during the luteal phase (Özer et al., 2025).

However, its effectiveness during the actual menstrual period appears more limited than that of some other essential oils, such as grapefruit. Although bergamot significantly improved mood-related outcomes and supported nervous system function, it did not significantly reduce total Menstrual Symptom Questionnaire (MSQ) scores or sub-dimensions related to active menstrual pain. Therefore, current evidence supports bergamot primarily as an intervention for premenstrual distress and mood disturbances rather than as a main treatment for acute primary dysmenorrhea cramps (Özer et al., 2025).

Clinical Effectiveness of Grapefruit

Clinical evidence suggests that grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*) essential oil is effective in managing both premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and active menstrual symptoms. Randomized controlled trials

have shown that inhalation of pure grapefruit oil significantly reduced total Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) scores, including depressive symptoms, anxiety, fatigue, and pain perception. Unlike bergamot, grapefruit also significantly improved Menstrual Symptom Questionnaire (MSQ) scores, particularly by reducing menstrual pain and the need for coping strategies to manage cramps (Özer et al., 2025).

These effects are largely attributed to limonene, the major bioactive constituent of grapefruit, which possesses analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. In addition to relieving uterine cramps, grapefruit may reduce menstruation-related stress and fatigue, making it a promising complementary intervention for improving women's quality of life during both the luteal and menstrual phases (Özer et al., 2025).

Comparative Effectiveness of Essential Oils in the Management of Primary Dysmenorrhea

Following a comprehensive review of the available clinical evidence, all essential oils included in this review demonstrated beneficial effects in alleviating menstrual pain associated with primary dysmenorrhea. Nevertheless, variations exist in their underlying mechanisms, methods of administration, and the robustness of the clinical evidence supporting their efficacy.

Table X. Comparison of the Clinical Effectiveness of Essential Oils in the Management of Primary Dysmenorrhea

Essential Oil	Predominant Route of Administration	Main Therapeutic Effects Reported	Strength of Clinical Evidence
Peppermint	Aromatherapy/inhalation;	Reduces pain intensity,	High

	Oral	alleviates uterine spasms, and improves gastrointestinal symptoms	
Ginger	Oral	Reduces menstrual pain through anti-inflammatory mechanisms comparable to NSAIDs	High
Cinnamon	Oral; Aromatherapy	Reduces pain intensity and associated menstrual symptoms through antispasmodic effects	Moderate-High
Rose	Aromatherapy/Massage	Reduces pain, anxiety, and accompanying symptoms such as fatigue and headache	Moderate
Lavender	Aromatherapy/Inhalation; Massage	Reduces pain intensity and promotes relaxation through anxiolytic and sedative effects	High
Clary Sage	Aromatherapy/Inhalation	Alleviates dysmenorrheic symptoms, enhances relaxation, and reduces psychological distress	Moderate
Chamomile	Oral	Reduces pain intensity, menstrual bleeding, and associated dysmenorrhea symptoms	High
Adas	Oral	Reduces pain through anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic mechanisms comparable to NSAIDs	High
Bergamot	Aromatherapy/Inhalation	Reduces premenstrual distress, anxiety, irritability, and pain perception while promoting emotional well-being	Moderate
Grapefruit	Aromatherapy/Inhalation	Reduces menstrual pain, anxiety, fatigue, and PMS symptoms, while decreasing reliance on coping strategies	Moderate-High

Based on the reviewed evidence, lavender, chamomile, peppermint, and fennel demonstrated the most consistent clinical effectiveness in reducing pain intensity associated with primary dysmenorrhea. Lavender was particularly effective in alleviating pain while promoting relaxation and reducing anxiety. Chamomile and fennel exhibited notable anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic effects, whereas peppermint provided potent analgesic benefits through menthol-mediated reduction of uterine contractions and pain perception. Ginger, cinnamon, and grapefruit also

showed promising outcomes. Ginger and cinnamon primarily exerted their effects through the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis involved in the pathogenesis of primary dysmenorrhea, while grapefruit demonstrated benefits in reducing both menstrual pain and accompanying psychological symptoms, including anxiety and fatigue. In contrast, rose, clary sage, and bergamot appeared to provide greater psychophysiological benefits by enhancing relaxation, alleviating stress, and improving emotional well-being during the menstrual cycle. Despite the therapeutic potential of all reviewed essential oils, variations in study design, dosage, intervention duration, and methods of administration limit direct comparisons across studies.

Comparative Analysis of Essential Oils

A comparative analysis was conducted to evaluate the relative advantages of each essential oil based on three key aspects: pharmacological mechanisms, clinical evidence, and potential for development as a complementary therapy for primary dysmenorrhea.

Comparison of Pharmacological Mechanisms

The essential oils reviewed exhibit distinct yet complementary mechanisms of action. Ginger demonstrates the broadest pharmacological activity by simultaneously inhibiting the COX and LOX pathways through gingerol and shogaol. Peppermint provides rapid analgesia through TRPM8 activation, in addition to its anti-inflammatory effects. Cinnamon primarily suppresses COX-2 and inflammatory mediators, whereas rose and lavender mainly exert antispasmodic, anxiolytic, and neuromodulatory effects that may reduce pain perception and improve relaxation (Zhao et al., 2022; Negi

et al., 2021; ; Koohpayeh et al., 2021; Song & Oh, 2025).

Comparison of Clinical Evidence

Among the reviewed essential oils, ginger and lavender have the strongest clinical evidence, supported by multiple randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses demonstrating significant reductions in pain scores. Peppermint also shows favorable clinical outcomes, particularly when applied through aromatherapy massage. Cinnamon is supported mainly by mechanistic and in vivo studies, while larger clinical trials are still needed to confirm the effectiveness of rose essential oil (Song & Oh, 2025; Negi et al., 2021; Lagzian et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2020; Koohpayeh et al., 2021).

Comparison of Development Potential

All reviewed essential oils exhibit favorable safety profiles at therapeutic doses used in aromatherapy. Ginger has the greatest development potential because of its dual anti-inflammatory mechanism, strong clinical evidence, wide availability, and low production cost. Peppermint is promising as a fast-acting analgesic, cinnamon as a natural anti-inflammatory agent, and lavender and rose as holistic therapies that combine pain relief with stress and anxiety reduction (Negi et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020; Song & Oh, 2025; Koohpayeh et al., 2021).

Table 5
Comparative Analysis of Essential Oils for the Management of Primary Dysmenorrhea

Parameter	Peppermint	Ginger	Cinnamon	Rose	Lavender
Anti-inflammatory activity	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Antispasmodic activity	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
Analgesic activity	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Clinical evidence	Moderate	Strong	Limited	Moderate	Strong
Safety	Good	Good	Good	Excellent	Excellent
Development potential	High	Very High	High	Moderate	High

Note: ✓✓✓ = strong; ✓✓ = moderate; ✓ = weak.

Note: Derived from the present study.

Most Promising Essential Oils for Primary Dysmenorrhea

Based on their pharmacological mechanisms, clinical evidence, safety profiles, and development potential, ginger, peppermint, and lavender emerged as the most promising essential oils for managing primary dysmenorrhea.

1. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) ranked first because of its dual inhibition of the COX-2 and LOX pathways, extensive clinical evidence, broad availability, and low production cost, making it the most practical complementary therapy (Negi et al., 2021; Meilani et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2020).

2. Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) ranked second owing to its rapid analgesic action through TRPM8 activation and strong antispasmodic effects, making it particularly effective for acute menstrual pain (Zhao et al., 2022; Lagzian et al., 2025; Fatwa et al., 2025; Kusnianto et al., 2023).

3. Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) ranked third because of its excellent safety profile and strong clinical evidence. Although its anti-inflammatory effects are less direct, its anxiolytic and sedative properties may reduce pain perception and enhance the effectiveness of aromatherapy, particularly when combined with ginger or peppermint (Song & Oh, 2025; Kumalasari et al., 2022; Fatwa et al., 2025; Saud et al., 2022).

Table 6
Ranking of the most promising essential oils for primary dysmenorrhea

Ranking	Essential Oil	Main Advantages	Rationale
1	Ginger (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	Dual COX-2 and LOX inhibition; strongest clinical evidence	Broadest mechanism, consistent clinical efficacy, abundant availability
2	Peppermint (<i>Mentha piperita</i>)	Rapid TRPM8-mediated analgesia; potent antispasmodic effect	Fast onset and effective for acute menstrual pain
3	Lavender (<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>)	Excellent safety; anxiolytic and sedative effects	Strong clinical evidence and synergistic potential in aromatherapy

Note: Derived from the present study.

Conclusions

This systematic literature review demonstrated that essential oils have considerable potential as complementary therapies for primary dysmenorrhea because of their anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antispasmodic, and neuromodulatory properties. Overall, the reviewed essential oils effectively reduced menstrual pain and improved associated symptoms with relatively favorable safety profiles, supporting their role as adjunctive non-pharmacological interventions.

Comparative analysis showed that ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) had the strongest overall potential due to its well-established pharmacological mechanisms, consistent clinical evidence, broad availability, and low cost. Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) demonstrated rapid analgesic and antispasmodic effects, whereas lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) showed the most consistent clinical evidence together with anxiolytic and relaxation benefits. Other essential oils, including cinnamon, chamomile, bergamot, clary sage, and rose, also exhibited promising therapeutic effects, although supporting clinical evidence remains limited. Despite these encouraging findings, heterogeneity in study design, intervention protocols, and outcome measures limits direct comparisons across studies. Therefore, further standardized randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes and long-term safety evaluations are needed to strengthen the evidence base and support clinical application.

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Artificial Intelligence (if not applicable, delete this section)

Generative Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT) was used during the preparation of this manuscript between May and June 2026. The tool was used to improve English grammar and academic writing style, enhance sentence clarity and coherence, assist with translation between Indonesian and English, refine the organization of sections, and provide suggestions for improving the presentation of the systematic literature review. Typical prompts included requests to improve academic language, translate manuscript sections while preserving their original meaning, summarize scientific information, and revise the manuscript to comply with the target journal's formatting requirements. No data, results, analyses, or scientific conclusions were generated solely by artificial intelligence. All AI-assisted outputs were carefully reviewed, verified, edited, and approved by the authors, who assume full responsibility for the accuracy, originality, and integrity of the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author contribution statement

All authors declare that the final version of this paper was read and approved.

Authors and CRediT Roles: H.K.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Literature Search, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. A.P.: Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. M.H.F.: Validation, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing. A.K.: Supervision, Project Administration, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing.

The total contribution percentage for this paper was as follows: H.K. 30%; A.P. 30%; M.H.F. 20%; and A.K. 20%.

Data availability statement

Data sharing is not applicable, since no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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